

Paradata Conveys Understanding of Workflows and Facilitates the Reuse of Research Data in the Arts and Humanities: The CAPTURE Project

Project note

Isto Huvila

Department of ALM, Uppsala University

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Abstract

Project CAPTURE, funded by the European Research Council, has investigated the relatively unexplored question of what information about the workflows involved in creating, managing and using research data is required for data to be reusable in the future. This cross-disciplinary, multi-methods research underlines the risk of producing documentation that is of little use. It also emphasises the importance of making existing information findable and generating new documentation only on such aspects of workflows that otherwise remain undocumented. The project's findings also underscore differences in the perspectives of data creators, managers and users, indicating that the documentation generated by data creators and kept in repositories is not always well understood by data users or usable. Finally, the work carried out by the CAPTURE project points to the need for conceptual clarity. We discuss paradata both as a form of information on workflows, processes and practices, and as a framework concept to discuss how people give and receive information about workflows, processes and practices in general, in research and beyond.

Keywords: paradata, workflows, processes, documentation, research data, data reuse

Paradata förmedlar förståelse för arbetsflöden och underlättar återanvändning av forskningsdata inom humaniora: CAPTURE-projektet

Sammanfattning

Det av Europeiska forskningsrådet finansierade forskningsprojektet CAPTURE har undersökt den relativt outforskade frågan om vilken information om arbetsflöden för skapande, hantering och användning av forskningsdata som är nödvändig för att data ska kunna återanvändas i framtiden. Denna tvärvetenskapliga forskning understryker risken med att producera dokumentation som är av liten nytta. Den betonar också vikten av att göra den redan existerande informationen sökbar och att endast generera ny dokumentation om sådana aspekter av arbetsflöden som annars förblir odokumenterade. Vidare understryker projektets resultat skillnader i perspektiven hos dataskapare, förvaltare och användare, vilket indikerar att den dokumentation som genereras av dataskapare och förvaras i dataarkiv inte alltid är väl förstådd och användbar för dataanvändare. Slutligen pekar arbetet i CAPTURE-projektet på behovet av begreppsmässig klarhet. Vi diskuterar paradata både som en form av information om arbetsflöden, processer och praktiker, och som ett ramverksbegrepp för att diskutera hur människor informerar och blir informerade om arbetsflöden, processer och praktiker.

Nyckelord: paradata, arbetsflöden, processer, dokumentation, forskningsdata, återanvändning av data

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Introduction

Data reuse in the arts and humanities requires an understanding not only of what the data is about, but also how it was conceived, for what purposes it was collected or created, and how it has been processed and used since its creation (e.g. Voss 2012; Faniel and Yakel 2017; Huvila 2022a). Project CAPTURE, funded by the European Research Council, inquired into the previously relatively unexplored question of exactly what information about the workflows involved in creating, managing and using research data is necessary for data to be reusable in the future (Huvila and Ekman 2024). In parallel, CAPTURE investigated how this information can be captured in both efficient and sufficiently comprehensive ways to support data reuse. Data on data creation and manipulation processes is articulated in the project as paradata (Börjesson, Sköld, and Huvila 2020). This term has notably been used in survey research (Schenk and Reuß 2024) and cultural heritage visualisation. In the latter, the London Charter and Seville Principles (Carrillo Gea et al. 2013) have emerged as two influential documents that stipulate the foundations for documenting visual representations in archaeological and cultural heritage-related contexts, underlining the importance of documenting not only visualisations themselves, but also the intellectual decisions and actions taken to produce them. More recently, the concept has been introduced in the context of research data (Huvila 2022a), and archives and records management (Davet, Hamidzadeh, and Franks 2023).

The purpose of CAPTURE was to create new knowledge and develop our understanding of how paradata is created and used. It also aimed to develop and test methods to capture paradata in research workflows. The results provide a basis for creating standards, as well as tools, for managing paradata and advances in data-intensive research, especially in fields that use heterogeneous research data from different cultural, organisational, temporary and cultural origins.

Paradata as a framework concept and form of data

One of the first tasks in the CAPTURE project was to engage in conceptual and theoretical work (see for example Sköld, Börjesson, and Huvila 2022; Huvila 2022a) relating to the concept of paradata and the way it is used and understood in different domains. The aim was to contribute to the development of paradata as a theoretical and practical concept. While references to the notion of paradata across disciplines show many similarities, there are also differences stemming from the variety of concerns being addressed (Sköld, Börjesson, and Huvila 2022; Cameron, Franks, and Hamidzadeh 2023).

In a concrete sense, paradata can be used to refer to a specific type of data that differs from both data and metadata. The term can also be understood in a theoretical sense as a means to conceptualise diverse forms of data or information

that can contribute knowledge of different types of processes, practices and workflows (Andersson, Huvila, and Sköld 2024; Huvila, Andersson, Sköld, and Liu 2024). Both approaches are fruitful, directing attention to the general need to convey understanding of workflows and highlighting the diverse explanatory functions of specific pieces of information (or data) that help provide such an understanding. The two approaches do, however, serve distinct purposes, and as such, deserve to be kept apart from each other. The problem with the first approach is that the empirical explorations of how paradata works in practice demonstrate how one person's paradata is likely to be another person's data and vice versa. For example, a description of the process of analysing a tissue sample is paradata for a scientist, but can function as data for a scholar of scientific practices. Therefore, rather than defining paradata by dichotomising it with other types of data and data-about-data, in the latter sense as a category of information, it is more fruitful to understand paradata as a category of conceptual and physical objects that can be appropriated, insofar as they are informative of processes and practices (Huvila 2025), rather than as a distinct kind of information or data.

The importance of documenting just enough

One major challenge for capturing and preserving paradata is that, when it comes to understanding specific aspects of workflows, individual data users' needs vary across situations. Without sufficient documentation on how scholars and other data creators and users have created, understood and interpreted data, there is a risk of ending up in what has been described as a digital dark age (Bollacker 2010), a situation where hard-to-reach and hard-to-find "dark data" becomes dominant (Geser and Niccolucci 2016; Anichini and Gattiglia 2015). Lack of contextual information about the creation of research data—both digital and non-digital—can, in the worst-case scenario, lead to the proliferation of substandard and hard-to-interpret datasets that may not support future research or foster the creation of new scholarly knowledge.

The practical goal of CAPTURE has been to support the implementation of national, European and global policies on data management and open data by enhancing our understanding of paradata and research-process documentation (see for example Beck and Neylon 2012; DCC 2017; Kansa and Kansa 2011; Gilby et al. 2022). In parallel, case studies of paradata in a broad range of disciplinary contexts (for example in Huvila, Andersson, and Sköld 2024b; Bruseker, Doerr, and Theodoridou 2017) have contributed to more efficient sharing and reuse of data in discipline-specific, thematic and interdisciplinary knowledge ecosystems and repositories.

The empirical focus of the project was archaeology. As a highly cross-disciplinary field operating with a broad variety of data from diverse disciplinary origins, ranging from material remains to textual scholarship, biology and

geophysics, it provides a fruitful context to inquire into the complexities of sharing knowledge on workflows. Many of the key challenges relating to data reuse and open data are prominently visible in archaeology (D’Andrea 2023). The benefits of working towards greater intellectual accessibility to datasets are equally apparent. Collecting data through excavations is a destructive activity that cannot be redone. The data-generation process in archaeology is different to many other humanities disciplines, where data can be generated or collected anew (Anichini and Gattiglia 2015), and newer, more precise or up-to-date data often substitutes older data for other purposes than historical research. This also means that archaeological datasets seldom become completely outdated and, as such, their reuse potential is extensive.

In addition to exploring archaeological data generation and documentation in depth, CAPTURE has engaged scholars from a range of disciplines in the inquiry of paradata and workflow documentation (e.g. Huvila, Andersson, and Sköld 2024b; Huvila and Sinnamon 2022; Huvila, Enwald, et al. 2022; Huvila, Greenberg, et al. 2021). As part of this work, the project has developed critical understanding of the social contexts and use of infrastructures emphasised in newer research agendas (e.g. Aloia et al. 2017; Lambourne et al. 2014) and empirical research (e.g. Mayernik et al. 2017). In parallel, it has created new knowledge of what data creators and users find important to document about data-related workflows, what explicit and implicit needs there are for documentation, and how the diverse needs and wishes of data creators and users can be satisfied in practice (Huvila, Andersson, Friberg, et al., forthcoming).

A key premise and insight from data documentation research is that it is impossible to document everything. There is also no limit to how much documentation can be generated. As a consequence, there is a risk that a lot of effort is invested in producing documentation with little relevance. The diversity of needs and the difficulty of anticipating them complicates the documentation of data-related workflows. Like all data (Mayernik and Acker 2018), paradata is bound to be incomplete. One significant challenge is how to document and preserve just enough, avoiding both over- and under-documentation. It is important to focus on identifying how the documentation effort can be minimised. This is especially critical for documentation that only serves assumed future purposes rather than immediate needs relating to data creation and its primary use. Much paradata can be captured automatically, but some aspects of workflows, in particular decisions and intellectual work, need to be documented manually. Further, it is important to examine what information might already be embedded in the data itself (Huggett 2012; Gant and Reilly 2017) and what aspects of workflows future users themselves can deduce using various types of non-literal “archaeological” or “forensic” post hoc methods (Kirschenbaum, Ovenden, and Redwine 2010) of inquiring into existing data. Before the CAPTURE project was initiated, research investigating

these approaches was carried out in isolation. There was little research covering the entire paradata phenomenon and how it links to communicating a more comprehensive understanding of research workflows.

Investigations of data creation and workflow reuse by archaeologists

The CAPTURE project and its approach are multidisciplinary. The participating researchers had experience and backgrounds in archival science, information science, archaeology and science studies. They helped approach paradata and the documentation of data-related workflows from multiple perspectives. Crucial aspects of understanding paradata and workflow documentation include how they link to the everyday work of their creators, managers and users; how different types of paradata are used to inform and how they inform their users; how they work when approached from within specific fields in the arts and humanities, and beyond.

The project used different methods to investigate the workflows, processes and practices that underpin the creation and use of research data within and outside of archaeology. It also proposed and developed methods to capture them. Studies have investigated paradata elements present in archaeological field reports and research data (e.g. Huvila, Sköld, and Börjesson 2021; Huvila, Börjesson, and Sköld 2022; Börjesson et al. 2022) as well as citations to methods literature and their usefulness in understanding research workflows (Huvila, Andersson, and Sköld 2022). Methods-wise, the project conducted ethnographic research; reviewed and tested previously proposed and newly developed methods for documenting paradata; and conducted a survey (Huvila, Andersson, and Sköld 2024a; Huvila, Andersson, Sköld, and Liu 2024) and interviews with key stakeholders (e.g. Börjesson, Huvila, and Sköld 2022).

Besides committing to conducting rigorous research *about* paradata, a critical question at the outset was how the CAPTURE project should think about and deal with paradata relating to the project itself. There were two obvious alternatives: try to document as much as possible, as meticulously as possible; or proceed as a normal research project would and at the end engage in an introspective analysis of what happened, how much and what kind of paradata was generated and preserved. The latter approach was chosen, as the alternative would have come with the apparent risk of us trying to do too much, resulting in something that could be done in this specific project, but would likely be unfeasible for any other project to follow. The work analysing paradata and documentation from CAPTURE hence started at the conclusion of the project. So far, it seems that a considerable amount of paradata was produced, and many of the processes and the progress of the work can be tracked from the available evidence. At the same

time, it is apparent that many crucial decisions were made, for example, during meetings and face-to-face discussions. The resulting paradata is inconsistent and may be absent, as we found in our analysis of other researchers' work.

It requires both effort and competence to exploit them (see Huvila, Olsson, et al., forthcoming).

There is a lot of paradata already out there—make sure not to lose it

The results from interview and survey studies, and our investigations into research publications and data, show that a lot of information qualifying as paradata on workflows is already available in different parts of typical research documentation. In archaeology, field reports are an important source of paradata as they are expected to document both the results and the investigation process. In addition to regular work descriptions, they convey knowledge – both directly and indirectly – of work processes, for example through descriptions of those processes and by providing information on participating actors. Another central source of paradata in archaeology is personal diaries and notebooks containing notes, observations and reflections on archaeological work. They correspond to the notebooks held by researchers elsewhere, especially in fieldwork and archival disciplines.

Photographs are another important source of paradata, in particular those showing ongoing work, the working environment and conditions (Huvila, Sköld, and Börjesson 2021). As with photographic analysis, close reading of datasets can provide information about their underlying workflows. Choice of words, descriptions and timestamps are just a few examples of elements in databases that incorporate knowledge of workflows (Börjesson et al. 2022). Since many of the traces of workflows, both in data and other research documentation, are often peripheral to major research outputs (Huvila, Sköld, and Andersson 2023)—even though standardisation offers multiple benefits for the findability and technical interoperability of data (e.g. Lins and Becker 2013)—there is a considerable risk that they are cleaned out in the process of normalising and standardising data. Early versions of research material that might seem unnecessary will be discarded in such a process (Börjesson et al. 2022). Although standards can permit the inclusion of multiple viewpoints through the documentation of parallel perspectives (Durost, Reich, and Girard 2022), such planned post hoc inclusion of concurrent and contradicting viewpoints does not solve the problem of losing something like an organic diversity of traces (Huvila, Sköld, and Andersson 2023) in the research material.

The fact that a lot of paradata already exists in available documentation means that the primary challenge in documenting processes is not necessarily how to

expand its quantity or scope. A critical problem is that paradata is scattered. It can be difficult to get a comprehensive understanding of the paradata that is available. In this respect, rather than generating more, it is more important to find existing paradata and make it findable for others. This requires an understanding of what information on workflows already exists, what is missing, and how it can be supplemented with whatever additional information is needed to convey an adequate understanding of data-creation workflows.

Dissimilar frames of reference complicate documentation

In addition to the problem that paradata might not always be available, it may also not meet the needs of its potential users. Different individuals often have slightly different views of what information is necessary and what a user can be expected to know. Infrastructural forms of backend work are seldom recognised and properly documented. For example, information on information management, standards and data structures is rarely documented in detail.

In addition, the results from the CAPTURE project show that data creators and users often have differing views on the type of paradata that is needed (Börjesson, Huvila, and Sköld 2022; Huvila, Andersson, and Sköld 2024b; Huvila, Juneström, et al. 2024). This aligns with earlier observations that understanding of the context of research data differs between data users and data creators (Faniel, Frank, and Yakel 2019). When a data creator is documenting paradata, the focus is often on details like what tools were used, who did what and who funded the work – details that seem obvious to the data creator to document (Huvila, Andersson, and Sköld 2024b). The resulting paradata follows their understanding of what is central to know about data-creation workflows and what is easy to document. In contrast, data users expect and need paradata that would help them understand workflows from the outset (Huvila, Andersson, Sköld, and Liu 2024).

Closing the gap between data creators, managers and users

The gap between what data creators and users consider important, meaningful and possible to document is a major challenge for documenting workflows, as well as for producing and preserving relevant paradata. It seems obvious that data users need better insights into specific workflows through relevant documentation, but also a general understanding of how research workflows function, as well as their underpinnings in the disciplines and research fields they engage with.

Although it has become a truism to underline that data is never raw, the dream of a universally usable, context-free data still very much underpins the way many researchers and non-researchers conceptualise it. Abandoning this idea not only in theory but also in practice is crucial if we are to create and preserve usable data and paradata. Just as data users need better insights into data generation and workflow processing, it is important that data creators understand how users approach their work, and what paradata is likely to be relevant to them. In many cases, even when data is thought to be comprehensible and reusable, it is, as Rösler (2020) points out in reference to Eco (2009), “under pressure” of the context of its creation. Rather than assuming that the documentation produced when creating data is adequate for its users, it is important that data creators focus on actual usage when creating and documenting data.

Data managers also need to be mindful. Whereas their obvious role is to bridge the gap between creators and users, there are indications that managers serve more to tame data, and make it manageable within contemporary technical and organisational infrastructures, than to foster data reuse. From this standpoint, it is critical we acknowledge that no one working with data on the journey from creation to use is neutral. Creating useful data documentation for others is difficult and becomes increasingly complicated when data creators, managers and users share little common ground (Huvila 2020). Even when it is created and managed with care, “taking” paradata into use (Huvila 2022b) is a task that requires effort and continuous critical reflection. It should not be taken lightly.

Read more about CAPTURE

Updates on the activities of the CAPTURE project, including workshops, online CAPTURE seminars with invited speakers and research results can be found on CAPTURE’s website (<http://www.u.se/en/research/capture>) and X (Twitter) @CAPTURE_ERC.

Data availability statement

Research data and publications produced by the CAPTURE project are available on the Digitala Vetenskapliga Arkivet portal at <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/project.jsf?dswid=1404&pid=project%3A1948>

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